

Guided Ultrasonic Waves: Emerging Methods (GUWEM)

Workshop held at Linslerhof, Germany, from 8 July to 11 July 2024.

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GUWEM Workshop

dates: 8 – 11 July 2024

at: Hotel Linslerhof
Linslerhof 1 • 66802 Überherrn • Germany

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The workshop

In Europe, we have a small but vibrant community of researchers working on the theory and practical use of elastic waveguides for material characterization, nondestructive testing, structural health monitoring and sensors. This workshop aims to provide a platform where these groups with diverse interests can meet and exchange ideas. Current advances in the field will be presented in the form of talks and posters. The goal is not only to exchange but also to interconnect, creating opportunities for valuable collaborations. The event is organized by the „Institut Langevin“ and the „Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)“. It is supported by the „Société Française d’Acoustique (SFA)“ and the „Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V. (DEGA)“.

Invited speakers

Matt Clark	University of Nottingham
Fabrice Lemoult	Institut Langevin, ESPCI Paris, PSL
Michael J. S. Lowe	Imperial College London
Vincent Pagneux	LAUM, CNRS, Université du Mans

Program: Monday, 8 July

15:00 **Arrival**

18:30 **Welcome Dinner**

Program: Tuesday, 9 July

- 9:00 Michael Lowe
Some practical needs and challenges for modelling guided waves (p. 5)
- 9:30 Armin Huber
Stiffness matrix method for modeling of guided waves in multilayered anisotropic plates: The Dispersion Calculator (p. 6)
- 10:00 Håvard Kjellmo Arnestad
Exploring the feasibility of using interval analysis to trace the dispersion curves of leaky guided waves (p. 7)
- 10:30 **Pause**
- 11:00 Clément Despres, Nicolas Quaegebeur, Michel Castaings, Christine Biateau, Patrice Masson, Éric Ducasse
Ultrasonic plate waves for material characterisation using single-sided air-coupled transducers (p. 8)
- 11:30 Marc Thelen, Nicolas Bochud, Manuel Brinker, Sambit Bapari, Jörg Weissmüller, Claire Prada, Patrick Huber
Recent developments in the elastic characterization of porous media by laser-excited elastic guided waves (p. 9)
- 12:00 Hafsa Diboune, Daniel A. Kiefer, Sylvain Mezil, Florian Lyonnet, François Bruno, Claire Prada
Guided waves in chromium coated zirconium cladding tubes (p. 10)
- 12:30 **Lunch break**
- 14:00 Wenqi Li, Paul Dryburgh, Carolina Guerra, Rikesh Patel, Richard J. Smith, Matt Clark
Using surface acoustic waves to image elasticity on metals (p. 11)
- 14:30 Luca De Marchi, Masoud Mohammadgholiha
Shaped Transducers for Guided Wave Inspections (p. 12)
- 15:00 Georg Watzl, Clemens Grünsteidl
Single-shot capable characterization of a layer by spatial harmonic excitation of the surface acoustic wave (p. 13)
- 15:30 **Pause**
- 16:00 Marc Deschamps, Eric Ducasse
Energy Velocity of Guided Waves in Immersed Multilayered Plates (p. 14)
- 16:30 Erlend Magnus Viggen, Håvard Kjellmo Arnestad
On acoustic radiation from subsonic surface vibrations (p. 15)
- 17:00 Per Lunde
Diffraction effects in ultrasonic beam transmission of a fluid-embedded solid plate (p. 16)
- 17:30 **Open exchange and posters**
- 18:30 **Dinner**

Program: Wednesday, 10 July

- 9:00 Fabrice Lemoult, Alexandre Delory, Daniel A. Kiefer, Maxime Lanoy, Antonin Eddi, Claire Prada
Guided elastic waves in soft elastomers: on the role of viscoelasticity and deformation (p. 17)
- 9:30 Clemens Grünsteidl, Georg Watzl, Katharina Burgholzer, Martin Rzyzy
Guided waves dispersion in piezoelectric plates: Experiment and theory (p. 18)
- 10:00 Pierre Chantelot, Alexandre Delory, Claire Prada, Fabrice Lemoult
Wave propagation in a soft fluid waveguide (p. 19)
- 10:30 **Pause**
- 11:00 Jakub Spytek, Lukasz Pieczonka
Local wavenumber imaging for damage detection in anisotropic structures (p. 20)
- 11:30 Julien de Rosny, Claire Prada, Maxime Farin, Lynda Chehami, Emmanuel Moulin
Passive plate monitoring (p. 21)
- 12:00 Wendwoga Fulgence Nikiema, Natalie Rauter
Interaction of guided Ultrasonic Waves with delaminations in Fiber Metal Laminates represented by contact definition (p. 22)
- 12:30 **Lunch break**
- 14:00 Jannis Bulling
Mass Lumping for Scaled Boundary Polygonal Elements (p. 23)
- 14:30 Evrripides Georgiades, Michael J.S. Lowe, Richard V. Craster
Computing leaky Lamb waves using spectral collocation (p. 24)
- 15:00 Sascha Thielges, Dimitri Rothermel, Marius Riedl, Martin Schuppmann, Leon Steven, Thomas Schuster
Intelligent sensor-technology to detect and quantify dangerous damage over large distances in inaccessible areas by using long range multiparameter ultrasound-computed tomography (INTACT) (p. 25)
- 15:30 **Pause**
- 15:45 **Social event**
- 19:00 **Dinner**

Program: Thursday, 11 July

- 9:00 Vincent Pagneux
Resonances at free edges for Lamb waves in continuous elasticity or elastic lattice (p. 26)
- 9:30 Leander Claes, Mareen Wippermann
Analysis of guided acoustic waves in periodically structured plates (p. 27)
- 10:00 Daniel A. Kiefer, Sylvain Mezil, Claire Prada
Multiplicity of dispersion spectra of anisotropic elastic plates near zero-group-velocity points (p. 28)
- 10:30 **Pause**
- 11:00 Sylvain Mezil, Hafsa Diboune, Daniel A. Kiefer, Angèle Niclas, Claire Prada
Zero-Group-Velocity Lamb modes in a thickness gradient (p. 29)
- 11:30 Carlos-Omar Rasgado-Moreno, Panpan Xu, Madis Ratassepp
Experimental challenges of guided wave tomography based on full waveform inversion for a pipe bend (p. 30)
- 12:00 Jan-Willem Vrolijk, Arno Volker
Non-contact inspection of composites and metallic parts using Lamb waves with a MEMS-sensor array (p. 31)
- 12:30 **Lunch break**
- 14:00 **Departure**

Posters and open exchange session

Posters will be displayed in a central place for the entire duration of the workshop. All participants are invited to bring new or old posters on guided waves to incentivize discussions. Moreover, there will be a slot for “open exchange” (Tuesday at 17:30) where participants are invited to exchange vis-à-vis about their work and which also invites to visit the posters.

List of announced posters:

- 1 Immanuel Roßteutscher, Thorsten Uphues, Klaus Drese
Transformer-based Signal Processing (p. 32)
- 2 Daniel A. Kiefer, Sylvain Mezil, Claire Prada
Local resonances and transverse-group-velocity waves in a silicon wafer (p. 33)

Some practical needs and challenges for modelling guided waves

Michael Lowe

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Models for calculating the properties of guided elastic waves have been developed for more than a century. The literature preserves a huge number of publications covering an active history of most of this period. This has been driven by applications needs across many interests, including geomechanics, non-destructive testing, structural health monitoring, and materials characterisation. The wide literature reflects the fact that the calculations are not easy, and our current modelling capabilities have been reached after much iteration and evolution. Even so, after resolving many of the challenges, we are left with some important modelling needs that are not yet resolved satisfactorily, while the application interests continue to extend to increasingly complex waveguides and behaviours.

It would be an impossible task to review the whole history of the challenges and the solutions. However it is interesting and instructive to remind ourselves of some of the motivations for models and of the difficulties that need to be overcome in order to deliver useful results. The presentation will focus on a few examples of practical application interests that impose challenges to the models, in particular in the author's research area of non-destructive testing. Some of these have been solved satisfactorily, while others would benefit from improvement of the models, particularly from the point of view of the "black box" kinds of calculations that are needed for users in industry.

Stiffness matrix method for modeling of guided waves in multilayered anisotropic plates: The Dispersion Calculator

Armin Huber

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In recent years, research on the modeling of guided waves has made a significant push forward. This is evident by the fact that at least five softwares or code packages have been released since 2018. This is outstanding considering that prior to this date, only the commercial DISPERSE [1] (early 1990s) and the free GUIGUW [2] software (2011) existed. Along with the release of new tools, the computation methods used by these tools have evolved too. While older tools tend to apply traditional root-finding methods such as the Global Matrix Method (GMM → DISPERSE, ElasticMatrix [3]) or the more recent Stiffness Matrix Method (SMM → Dispersion Calculator (DC) [4]), the newer tools tend to rely more on discretizing methods such as the Semi-analytical Finite Element Method (SAFE → SAFEDC [5]), the Spectral Collocation Method (SCM → future version of DISPERSE), and the Spectral Element Method (SEM → GEWtool [6]). The Dispersion Box [7] is notable for the fact that six computation methods can be used: SAFE, GMM, SMM, Hybrid Compliance-Stiffness Matrix Method (HCSMM), Legendre Polynomial Method (LPM), and Fifth Order Shear Deformation Theory (5-SDT).

The main reasons for switching to discretizing methods are that these can model waveguides with arbitrary cross sections and that, in case of SCM and SEM, no modal solution can be missed when obtaining dispersion curves. However, SMM as a root-finding method has the advantage that accuracy remains constant at the desired level, whereas in discretizing methods, it depends on the number of sample or collocation points, thereby losing accuracy as the mode shape becomes more complex with increasing frequency. After all, the SMM-implementation in DC has reached a high level of speed and robustness of dispersion curve tracing for guided waves in multilayered anisotropic plates, which allows it to keep up with other tools and computation methods. This is made possible by using mode family specific dispersion equations combined with a robust dispersion curve tracing algorithm [8]. Currently, the numerical model of DC is extended to isotropic rods and pipes. A live demonstration of DC may convince the audience that it is a capable and valuable tool for the community.

References

- [1] M. J. S. Lowe and B. Pavlakovic, DISPERSE, (early 1990s).
- [2] A. Marzani and P Bocchini, GUIGUW, (2011).
- [3] D. R. Ramasawmy, B. T. Cox and B. E. Treeby, ElasticMatrix, (2020).
- [4] A. M. A. Huber, Dispersion Calculator, (2018).
- [5] M. Liu, SAFEDC, (2022).
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Exploring the feasibility of using interval analysis to trace the dispersion curves of leaky guided waves

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Complete knowledge of the dispersion and attenuation characteristics of guided waves is often crucial to the development of ultrasonic guided wave techniques. Finding these propagation characteristics requires solving an underlying eigenvalue problem, with a modern example technique being spectral collocation schemes. Still, the traditional approach for the leaky Lamb wave problem is to find and trace the roots of the characteristic equations, e.g., for asymmetric leaky Lamb modes:

$$\frac{\tan(\gamma_p h)}{\tan(\gamma_s h)} + \frac{4k_x^2 \gamma_s \gamma_p}{(k_x^2 - \gamma_s^2)^2} + i \frac{\rho_f k_s^4 \gamma_p}{\rho \sqrt{k_f^2 - k_x^2} (k_x^2 - \gamma_s^2)^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\tan(\gamma_s h)} = 0, \quad (1)$$

which is an ill-conditioned problem that requires some level of manual tuning of the algorithm. For fluid-loaded plates, the dispersion curve tracing is more challenging because modal solutions are sought in the complex wavenumber plane.

Interval analysis (IA) is a technique employed in a variety of fields, including root-finding. Instead of working with precise numbers, the computations are carried forward using intervals. This leads to another form of arithmetic where also the output is given by an interval. To the author's knowledge, IA has only seen limited application for guided waves, but one publication from 2013 applies *real-valued* interval-Newton approach to find roots of the characteristic equation [1], notably without attenuation.

In this work, we apply *complex-valued* IA to the characteristic leaky Lamb wave equations in a proof-of-concept fashion. Attenuation is naturally incorporated, enabled by the development of interval versions of the complex \sqrt{z} and $\tan(z)$ functions, exemplified in panel **a)** and **b)**. This allows for direct and reliable identification of large regions within the search space that *cannot* contain a root solution. Panel **c)** and **d)** shows this for frequency ω , wavenumber $k_{x, re}$, and attenuation $k_{x, im}$. Strong indications about the location of roots and discontinuities are also obtained, which can be further refined by bisecting the candidate intervals. Furthermore, typical IA problems are investigated, namely the wrapping and dependency problems.

Figure 1: Panel **a)** & **b)** shows the interval and point-based $\tan(z)$ function. Panel **c)** shows the Eq.(1) evaluated over frequency-wavenumber for a 1 cm thick steel plate, whereas panel **d)** is evaluated over wavenumber-attenuation at 1.5 MHz for the same plate in water. The color of each small box (complex interval) indicates what the interval contains.

References

- [1] F. Bause, A. Walther, J. Rautenberg, and B. Henning. "Reliable computation of roots in analytical waveguide modeling using an interval-newton approach and algorithmic differentiation." *IEEE TUFFC* 60.12 (2013), pp. 2597–2606. DOI: 10.1109/TUFFC.2013.2858.

Ultrasonic plate waves for material characterisation using single-sided air-coupled transducers

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This paper investigates the sensitivity of Lamb wave modes to elastic moduli and thickness of plate-like components for characterisation purposes. Isotropic materials are considered, and sensitivity functions are derived as gradients of wavenumbers with respect to material parameters to be further optimised. They are useful to define the most suitable range of wavenumber values that should be generated and detected by a transmitter and a receiver, respectively. Consequently, the wavenumber spectrum allows the size of the transducers to be defined, as well as their angle with respect to the normal of the plate-sample, for multi-modal generation-detection.

Air-coupled capacitive ultrasonic transducers (ACUTs) are then built according to wavenumber spectra predicted for several types of materials. Experimental measurements are made using this pair of ACUTs, which simultaneously generate and detect several Lamb modes along the plate-samples. The receiver is moved along the path of propagation, i.e. parallel to the sample; signals are picked-up and post-processed to extract the modes phase velocities in the frequency range of the transducers. These velocities are finally used as input data for an inverse problem, which optimises the material stiffness and/or the sample thickness. Results are presented for a single plate made of Perspex and for an adhesive bond joining two metallic substrates.

Recent developments in the elastic characterization of porous media by laser-excited elastic guided waves

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The elastic characterization of porous systems is challenging with traditional testing methods. For instance, the widely applied pulse echo method requires in general a viscous coupling medium [1]. Due to the high capillary pressure of porous materials, the fluid would be imbibed into the pore network which in turn would lead to a change of the mechanical properties, prohibits further investigations and limits the feasibility of in-situ measurements, which are often of interest for functionalized porous materials. In addition, the full mechanical characterization of anisotropic systems, requires measurements in different crystallographic directions and is certainly problematic for flat porous materials.

Laser-excited elastic guided waves provide a promising alternative to overcome these obstacles due to the multimodal, dispersive and contactless nature of this technique.

Figure 1: (a) Dispersion of a pSi membrane with conical (a1) and cylindrical pores (a2). (b) Shift of the first ZGV of a porous palladium sample due to the exposure to hydrogen.

This has been demonstrated in a recent study of porous silicon (pSi). We investigated the complex mechanics and the influence of the pore's conicity [2]. The conicity can be actively influenced by the synthesis process parameters and arbitrary pore profiles can be generated (Fig. 1a).

In another experiment we took advantage of the enhanced in-situ capabilities and high resolution of laser-excited elastic guided waves. The elastic modulus of porous palladium, a system of randomly oriented ligaments, can be drastically changed by the absorption of hydrogen [3]. This has been studied by tracking the zero-group velocity (ZGV) frequencies (Fig. 1b).

References

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- [2] M. Thelen, N. Bochud, M. Brinker, C. Prada, and P. Huber. "Laser-excited elastic guided waves reveal the complex mechanics of nanoporous silicon." *Nature communications* 12.1 (2021).
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Guided waves in chromium coated zirconium cladding tubes

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Non-destructive testing (NDT) is an essential tool for guaranteeing the integrity and safety of structures. Surface waves have been studied extensively for this purpose, yielding successful applications such as crack detection or thickness measurement. These waves are efficiently generated by laser impact and well detected by laser interferometry, providing broadband and non-contact measurements.

In the present study, we used surface waves to evaluate the mechanical properties of a chromium coating deposited on a zirconium alloy (M5¹) cladding tube. As chromium has a much higher shear wave velocity than M5 ($V_{T_{\text{Chromium}}}/V_{T_{\text{M5}}} \approx 1.75$) the surface wave velocity strongly depends on frequency. In the middle-frequency range, characterized by shear wavelengths smaller than the tube thickness but greater than the chromium coating thickness, the surface wave is dispersive. Eventually, more than one surface mode can be observed, depending on the properties of the chromium layer. Elastic waves were generated by an 8 ns pulsed Nd-YAG laser source ($\lambda = 1064$ nm), focused into a line perpendicular to the tube axis. The normal displacement was then measured on the sample surface with a heterodyne interferometer [1]. The wave field was acquired by scanning the laser source along the tube axis and its 2D Fourier transform yields dispersion curves of axial guided modes up to 20 MHz. In order to model these waves, the elastic constants of M5 were determined from X-ray diffraction measurements and those of chromium were taken from the literature. Using these parameters, the theoretical dispersion curves were calculated with GEWtool [2] and compared to the measurements (Fig.1a). The excitability of each mode, estimated from its modal displacements (Fig.1b), appears in good agreement with the experiment. Measurements were achieved on different chromium layers that were then characterized by adjusting the dispersion curves.

(a) Experimental dispersion curves obtained on a 550 μm -thick M5 cladding tube with a 15 μm -thick chromium layer

(b) Excitability \times detectability curves computed for a 550 μm -thick M5 cladding tube with a 15 μm -thick chromium layer

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- [1] D. R. Eugène Dieulesaint. “Optical Detection of Sub-Angstrom Transient Mechanical Displacements.” *IEEE Ultrasonics Symposium IEEE* (1986), p. 525.
- [2] D. A. Kiefer. *Gewtool*. 2023. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10114243. (<https://github.com/dakiefer/GEWtool>).

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Using surface acoustic waves to image elasticity on metals

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Despite elasticity being a fundamental material property there aren't many convenient methods for measuring or imaging it. The current state of the art techniques don't lend themselves to imaging and tend to involve the expensive or destructive preparation of special samples which gives an incomplete picture of the true material properties.

In this paper we used spatially resolved acoustic spectroscopy of surface acoustic waves to determine and image the single crystal elasticity matrix of polycrystalline metals. We demonstrate a simple trick which allows us to extract a global C_{ij} without a-priori knowledge of the crystallographic orientation of the crystals. This enables us to determine C_{ij} both globally and locally without the special preparation of single crystals and allows us to image and track the elasticity across engineering materials as they evolve.

This technique, SRAS++, use laser ultrasound to generate and detect narrow band surface waves on the sample. The velocity is measured from the frequency spectrum of the waves generated. If C_{ij} is already known then the orientation of the crystals can be determined by measuring the velocity as a function of propagation direction. If C_{ij} is unknown then the velocities from a multitude of crystals, each with an unknown direction, can be combined to solve for C_{ij} and the crystal orientations simultaneously.

This has so far been demonstrated on cubic, hexagonal, and tetragonal crystal structures. Since the measurement technique is fast (> 1000 measurements per second) it can be used to image the crystal structure across the sample surface and monitor processes in-situ.

Shaped Transducers for Guided Wave Inspections

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Guided wave (GW)-based structural health monitoring (SHM) typically involves the deployment of numerous piezoelectric transducers on the component under inspection. This permanent setup enables on-demand acquisition of structural integrity data. However, inherent drawbacks include bulky hardware instrumentation, extensive cabling, complex signal processing demands, high power consumption, and consequently, substantial integration costs. Such drawbacks hinder the widespread application of GW technology in sectors like aerospace and automotive, where weight constraints are stringent. These limitations can be addressed through the adoption of transducers with inherent beam steering capabilities such as Frequency Steerable Acoustic Transducers (FSATs) [1, 2]. Achieving such beam steering capabilities entails shaping the electrodes of piezoelectric transducers in accordance with the dispersion properties of the waveguide, facilitating the selective generation of ultrasonic waves along desired directions based on the frequency spectrum of a single excitation signal. Additionally, it enables the automatic detection of wave propagation directions within the structure, requiring minimal hardware and software resources. Numerical and experimental validations of this concept is presented in this work. In addition to beam steering, beam focusing serves as another valuable tool for ultrasonic inspections. For instance, in scenarios where direct access to a critical area of a structure is impractical, focusing the wave energy at that specific point, referred to as hot-spot monitoring, can be advantageous. One proposed technique for achieving this is the time reversal method, wherein a sensor reverses the received signal from the actuator (in the time domain) then transmits it back. Since beam focusing necessitates the use of multiple piezoelectric transducers, an innovative approach for wave focusing based on shaping the transducer's electrode according to the time reversal principle can be employed. This approach aims to design a transducer that inherently concentrates the wave energy at a predetermined point, thereby overcoming the limitations associated with conventional methods. This study presents the numerical implementation of the proposed Time Reversing Transducer (TRT), along with potential avenues for future research and development.

Figure 1: Time Reversing Transducer

References

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Single-shot capable characterization of a layer by spatial harmonic excitation of the surface acoustic wave

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We present a single-shot capable method for the characterization of a layer on a substrate. Conclusions about the structure of layered samples can be drawn from the dispersion of their guided wave modes. Especially the classical problem of a layer on a half space has been extensively studied [1], and experimental techniques for layer characterization are well established [2, 3]. However, these typically require scanning the excitation or detection positions, limiting achievable measurement speeds.

With the presented method, the surface acoustic wave (SAW) dispersion can be resolved to a limited extent with only a single measurement, given sufficiently high signal-to-noise ratio. We use a pulsed laser, shaped into an array of equidistantly spaced lines on a sample's surface, to generate elastic waves. The surface displacement response is then detected with a vibrometer adjacent to the excitation pattern. This excitation arrangement leads to constructive interference of the SAW mode at a wavelength matching the line spacing, resulting in a distinct peak in the response spectrum. Additional harmonic peaks, corresponding to integer fractions of the fundamental wavelength, can also be observed given appropriate excitation conditions. As the line spacing and thereby the generated wavelengths are known, these frequency peaks can be mapped to discrete points on the SAW mode. An inverse problem can be solved to fit a model to the experimental data, resulting in the properties of the layer.

While this method provides only reduced information compared to a full dispersion relation scan, its considerably higher speed may make this technique advantageous in situations where limited a priori knowledge on the specimen is available. We demonstrate this technique for copper layers on epoxy and roll-cladded aluminum alloy plates and compare the results with dispersion relation scans and theoretical modeling.

Figure 1: (left): Illustration of the generation of spatial harmonic SAWs. (right): Discrete points on the SAW mode measured on Cu-coated ($35\mu\text{m}$, $70\mu\text{m}$) epoxy and comparison with a model.

References

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Energy Velocity of Guided Waves in Immersed Multilayered Plates

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The computation modes in fluid-loaded multilayer plates is generally done by a spatial approach, *i.e.* solutions are sought for a complex slowness. An alternative approach, less frequently employed, involves seeking solutions for complex frequencies. These frequencies correspond to plate resonances. They denote transient phenomena and the guided modes exhibit non-harmonic behavior. Consequently, conventional methods of averaging over time periods become unsuitable for calculating the means of energy quantities. In other words, the calculation of average fields cannot be reduced to a single average over a time period. To tackle this issue, for a predetermined mode, the average fields are obtained through a single averaging process applied to an arbitrary phase term. This averaging process renders independent the means of all energy quantities from the arbitrary origin phase. Subsequently, an additional integration across the thickness is conducted to derive total energy quantities. Doing this, the total average fields depend on both time and position on the surface plate. A set of four equations is derived from instantaneous and local energy balance equations. From these averages, the energy velocity can be directly calculated. The equations provide further insights into wave dispersion and damping along the guided wave ray, arising from viscoelastic losses and leakages in fluid.

On acoustic radiation from subsonic surface vibrations

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Surface vibrations moving with speed c_v will generate pressure waves in an adjacent fluid, as Fig. 1a shows. It is commonly held that these pressure waves radiate away from the surface only if the vibration is *supersonic* ($c_v > c_f$, where c_f is the fluid's sound speed), and that *subsonic* ($c_v < c_f$) vibrations only yield non-radiating evanescent waves. However, multiple works solving the exact dispersion equations of leaky Lamb and Rayleigh waves have found that even *subsonic* vibrations can yield radiating waves. A physical understanding of this phenomenon can be encapsulated into a simple yet exact radiation model [1] to supplement previous mathematical results.

Figure 1: **(a)** Unattenuated vibration (blue) radiating homogeneous plane wavefronts (orange). **(b)** Attenuated vibration radiating inhomogeneous plane wavefronts. Pale orange arrows indicate wave propagation direction (along which the wave amplitude is constant) and line thickness indicates amplitude.

This model encapsulates two interconnected key concepts. The first is that when surface vibrations radiate acoustic power into the fluid, the vibrations lose power and are *attenuated*. The second is that attenuated vibrations radiate *inhomogeneous* waves, where the amplitude changes exponentially along the wavefronts, as Fig. 1b shows. Such inhomogeneous waves propagate more slowly than homogeneous waves, thus permitting subsonic radiation. The model shows that there are three radiation subdomains: The radiating wave in the *supersonic domain* extends into the ‘near’ *subsonic domain* until it cuts off at the boundary to the ‘far’ *subsonic domain*. Evanescent waves are still valid solutions in the whole subsonic domain.

This radiation model partly explains puzzling results for subsonic A_0 Lamb waves [2], which either cut off below coincidence and then reappear at very low frequencies, or never cut off at all. Preliminary results show that radiation into solids is significantly more complicated than radiation into fluids: When the radiated P- and S-waves are inhomogeneous, the total intensity radiated from the vibrating surface no longer equals the sum of the individual P- and S-wave intensities [3].

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Diffraction effects in ultrasonic beam transmission of a fluid-embedded solid plate

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Diffraction effects in ultrasonic beam transmission of a fluid-embedded solid plate are studied theoretically and experimentally, at normal and oblique angles of beam incidence. The beam excites leaky Lamb waves in the plate that excites wavefields in the surrounding fluid, exhibiting distinct near- and farfield characteristics in the transmitted beam. Significant plate nearfield effects are observed for backward waves related to the fundamental thickness-extensional mode of the plate (TE1). This includes TE1 resonance frequency downshift, beam narrowing, signal enhancement, and distinct minima/maxima in the transmitted frequency spectrum. These effects are described by simulations and verified experimentally. Results are discussed for a 6.05 mm thick water-embedded steel plate, using sound beams over the 350-1000 kHz range, involving four leaky Lamb modes (S_{-2}, S_2, A_2, A_3). For the backward-wave mode associated with TE1 and S_{-2} , nearfield effects extend to hundreds of meters from the plate. At very far distances the wavefield approaches a plane-wave field. Nearfield diffraction characteristics depend on the transducer's ka -number, the source-plate and plate-receiver distances, the plate's thickness-frequency number and Poisson's ratio, the fluid and plate properties, and the angle of beam incidence. If not corrected for, diffraction effects may cause errors in ultrasonic characterization of thickness and material properties of plates and pipe walls using through-thickness resonant measurements.

Figure 1: Schematics of experimental water tank setup with transducer, steel plate and hydrophone; simulated beam transmission at normal beam incidence and 457 kHz (reflected field not shown); and measured and simulated frequency spectra of the plate's axial pressure transfer function, at normal beam incidence and hydrophone 10 cm from the plate. The vertical lines indicate the plane-wave cutoff frequencies of the associated Lamb modes of the traction-free plate, vibrating in vacuum.

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Guided elastic waves in soft elastomers: on the role of viscoelasticity and deformation

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The propagation of elastic waves in nearly incompressible material is characterized by a velocity V_L of longitudinal waves which is much higher than the velocity V_T of transverse waves. The guided elastic waves in a thin plate made of such a material present some peculiarities that we will discuss during this talk. For example, because of this big contrast between the two velocities, at low frequencies the SH_0 mode propagates at V_T while S_0 propagates at the plate velocity $V_P = 2V_T$, which is independent from the longitudinal velocity V_L despite its apparent longitudinal polarization [1].

We have performed experimental measurements of those modes in a soft plate made of a commercial silicone elastomer Ecoflex[®], with a contrast in velocities $V_L/V_T \approx 200$. A monochromatic source generates plane waves in a 60 cm \times 60 cm plate and a camera mounted with a narrow angle lens records a movie. Making use of common image post-processing techniques, the full in-plane displacement field is extracted and the two velocities V_T and V_P are easily measured [2].

The soft plate is then subject to a uniaxial tension with a stretch ratio reaching $\lambda = 2$. An induced anisotropy is observed and velocities do not vary linearly with λ . To explain those changes, one needs to take into account the acoustoelastic effect. It is derived from an hyperelastic constitutive law, which is based on a strain energy density function. For low stretch ratios ($\lambda \leq 1.1$), the experimental observations can be explained by the simplest model, *ie.* the NeoHookean model. However, for larger deformations, a more sophisticated hyperelastic model, involving the second principal invariant, as well as the rheology of the material are both needed [3].

Finally, dispersion curves of in-plane guided modes in a soft strip have also been measured. Theoretically, those dispersion curves can be computed as Lamb modes with an equivalent longitudinal velocity $V'_L = V_P$. In particular, some characteristic of these dispersion curves directly derive from previous velocities, notably the cut-off frequencies and the bar and Rayleigh velocities. Stretching this soft strip leads to changes in these dispersion curves and can be predicted with the same acoustoelastic framework [4, 5].

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Guided waves dispersion in piezoelectric plates: Experiment and theory

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In piezoelectric materials, elastic waves are coupled with electromagnetic waves. The basis for their description, are the acoustic and electromagnetic field equations coupled by a piezoelectric term [1]. In addition to the elastic stiffness matrix, the electric permittivity matrix and the piezoelectric coupling matrix are required to predict the linear behavior of a material. For waveguides, such as plates, additional boundary conditions for the electric field need to be fulfilled and affect the propagation of guided waves. Although piezoelectric materials are omnipresent in electronic products, e.g. in bandpass-filters for telecommunication, their characterization still poses challenges. Standard methods are based on electric impedance measurements on samples provided in special test geometries, and at different orientations, to disentangle the elastic, dielectric and piezoelectric properties [2]. However, especially for frequencies in the GHz range, the materials of interest often cannot be produced in the required form. Also, an in situ characterization is desired, as actual properties may be affected by details of the production process. Further open questions and challenges exist for the additional characterization of losses and their description using complex material matrices [3].

Unlike the standard techniques, which require electrical contact, laser-ultrasound (LUS) can be used to generate and detect waves, independent of electrical boundary conditions. LUS techniques also have proven feasible for GHz-range characterization of elastic materials including losses [4]. As a first step to address the challenges listed above, and to extend the LUS techniques to piezoelectric materials, we investigate guided waves in a piezoelectric plate. We implemented numerical solutions for the dispersion curves based on the spectral collocation method [5] and validated the solutions with LUS measurements [6], finite-element simulations and literature results [7]. Calculations and experiments are shown for different electrical boundary conditions [6] and directions of propagation. As test specimen 0.5 mm Lithium-Niobate wafers are used, where the electrical boundary conditions are set by depositing a layer of gold either on one, both or no side of the wafer.

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Wave propagation in a soft fluid waveguide

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Fluid filled pipes are ubiquitous in both man-made constructions and living organisms. In the latter, biological pipes have unique properties as their walls are made of soft, incompressible, highly deformable materials. Here, we experimentally investigate wave propagation in a model soft pipe: an elastomer strip coupled to a rigid water channel (figure 1). We first measure the wave's dispersion relation using synthetic Schlieren imaging, revealing its strong dependence on the pressure difference ΔP between the water and the ambient. Through a mechanical model that accounts for the material rheology and for the large static out-of-plane deformation of the strip [1], we evidence that ΔP affects wave propagation through an interplay between the creation of tension, orthogonal to the propagation direction, and curvature induced rigidity [2, 3]. We then discuss the relevance of this experiment in the biological setting, by pointing out the link between our measurements and the Moens-Korteweg velocity [4, 5] that describes the propagation of pulse waves in arteries. Finally, we impose a steady flow velocity U and show its influence on wave propagation, highlighting the breaking of spatial reciprocity.

Figure 1: Schematic of the experimental setup. The out-of-plane motion of the soft strip (in pink) is measured using synthetic Schlieren imaging.

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Local wavenumber imaging for damage detection in anisotropic structures

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Local wavenumber estimation (LWE) is a proven method for damage detection in thin-walled structures. It is a full-field imaging technique, which involves excitation of guided waves and measuring the responses of the wavefield at multiple spatial locations. The obtained space-time dataset is then processed using a set of filters, which enable mapping the local wavenumbers of a chosen wave mode in the spatial coordinates. Based on the local changes of wavenumber, the damage can be located and characterized. However, the existing LWE methods are designed for isotropic, rather than anisotropic, structures, which result in the spurious values of local wavenumber. In effect, these processing artifacts may hinder correct detection and characterization of defects. Therefore, in this work we propose an improved implementation of the local wavenumber estimation algorithm for anisotropic media (ALWE). The approach is based on the application of filters, which are tailored to the shape of directional profile of the wavefield in wavenumber domain. The working principle and efficiency of the proposed algorithm are illustrated on datasets coming from numerical simulations and experimental testing on anisotropic carbon fiber reinforced polymer laminates. We demonstrate that the proposed algorithm successfully compensates for the processing artifacts and enhances the overall quality of the wavenumber maps facilitating unequivocal damage detection. The local wavenumber maps obtained from anisotropic structure using LWE and ALWE are presented in Figures 1a and b respectively.

Figure 1: Local wavenumber maps obtained using (a) existing LWE algorithm and (b) a proposed ALWE variant.

Passive plate monitoring

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Detection and localization of unbounded contacts in industrial structures are crucial for safety. However, most structural health monitoring techniques are either invasive, power-consuming, or rely on time-varying baseline comparison. A passive acoustic method is proposed to localize unbounded contacts in plate-like structures, using the acoustic emissions by the contacts when they are excited by ambient noise. The technique consists of computing the correlation matrix of the signals measured by a set of receivers and applying to this matrix a beamforming algorithm accounting for flexural wave dispersion. To validate the technique, an experimental setup is developed in which three idealized unbounded contacts are created on a thin plate excited by a shaker. How the quality of the defect localization depends on the defect type, receiver number, and the characteristics of the noise is investigated. Finally, it is shown that the localization of unbounded contacts is possible using either an acoustic ambient noise source or a more realistic jet engine noise[1].

But noise can be also used to monitor the occurrence of defects in thin aluminum plates. A correlation matrix is estimated from noise vibrations recorded on a transducer array. Because the correlation matrix converges toward the Green's function, a defect is localized by applying a beamforming algorithm to the difference between the correlation matrices obtained with and without the defect. We successfully detect defects for different kinds of noise sources. Moreover, we show that this technique is robust to detect massive inclusions, holes, and cracks. With a vibrometer, we observe that the fidelity of the estimated transient responses strongly depends on the number of uncorrelated noise sources. Finally, we show that the defect is successfully localized even if the noise source distribution is not uniform, provided that it remains spatially stationary between the states with and without defect. A simple theoretical framework is proposed to interpret these results[2].

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Interaction of guided Ultrasonic Waves with delaminations in Fiber Metal Laminates represented by contact definition

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The nonlinear behaviour of guided wave propagation in fibre metal laminates (FML) is investigated in this current work. The generation of higher harmonics in FML is investigated from a numerical perspective and examined for plausibility with theoretical findings.

For this purpose, a numerical model of FML consisting of layers of steel and carbon fibre reinforced polymer is presented. Wave propagation is simulated in both undamaged and damaged models, with the first representing the reference model for comparison. The nonlinear behaviour is first investigated with a geometric nonlinearity by using the full GREEN-LAGRANGE strain tensor and therefore allowing large deformations.

The investigation of the nonlinear wave propagation is then continued with the modelling of delamination including contact definition between the interfaces, known in the literature as contact acoustic nonlinearity (CAN).

The evaluation of the results of the first case show the occurrence of second-harmonic on the FFT of the time signal response. However, this can only be detected by using symmetrical mode excitation. With antisymmetrical excitation, higher harmonic modes frequencies do not occur, which is consistent with theoretical findings. In the second case, the second harmonic is also observed. In addition, it appears that its amplitudes correspond to those of the first case. The effect of the CAN can be discerned in terms of amplitude for fourth harmonics.

Mass Lumping for Scaled Boundary Polygonal Elements

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Many modern ultrasonic methods in the fields of Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) and Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) require simulations in research. Researchers either use simulation data initially during development to investigate certain aspects, or the simulation process is directly part of the research task. Examples of the second case are inverse methods for parameter estimation, model-assisted probability of detection analysis or the generation of training data for AI algorithms. All these applications require algorithms that are as efficient as possible. For methods based on explicit time-step methods, a significant increase in efficiency can be achieved if a so-called lumped mass matrix can be used, which approximates the consistent mass matrix but is easier to invert.

The finite element method has been the subject of many studies on approximations of the mass matrix. In contrast, the lumped mass matrix in the context of the Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method (SBFEM) is a current field of research [1, 2]. In the time domain, the semi-analytical SBFEM is notable for its flexibility to be applied to polygonal meshes. In particular, image-based mesh generation using a quadtree algorithm is possible. In general, polygonal meshes have the same flexibility as triangular meshes, but polygonal meshes can have additional advantages such as greater tolerance to distortion.

In this contribution, the SBFEM formulation based on bubble functions [3] for the time domain is presented for two-dimensional elastic waves. The adjustments necessary for a good approximating lumped mass matrix are emphasized. Several grid generation methods for polygonal elements are shown. Figure 1 depicts the difference between the consistent mass matrix and the lumped mass matrix for a normal polygonal mesh. Finally, the accuracy of mass lumping for linear, quadratic and cubic shape functions is presented and the computational efficiency is demonstrated using exemplary waveguide geometries.

Figure 1: The two different mass matrices for the mesh on the right.

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Computing leaky Lamb waves using spectral collocation

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Guided waves are attractive for the inspection of many components and structures, with the component often partially in contact with other media or fully immersed or buried. In such guided wave inspections, energy is no longer necessarily confined within the boundaries of a waveguide, but rather leaks into the adjacent media, causing the guided wave to attenuate. Consequently, prior to selecting a guided mode for an effective inspection, it is crucial to study the leaky system and understand its dispersion and attenuation characteristics.

Significant challenges arise when trying to compute leaky waves due to both the complex wavenumber required to describe them and their amplitudes exponentially growing far into the surrounding media. This work introduces a Spectral Collocation Method (SCM) for the computation of leaky waves in immersed or buried structures, originally formulated for the computation of leaky waves in a waveguide immersed in fluid(s) [1], and then extended to a waveguide embedded in elastic solid(s) [2], that bypasses the challenges associated with the complex wavenumber and the exponential growth of leaky waves, and automates their computation. The presented methodology offers a simple and accurate "black box" approach for reliably computing all leaky waves and does not require any prior expertise or knowledge of the modes to be found by the user. Results of our method are validated against the commercially available software DISPERSE [3] and numerical experiments using Finite Elements (FE).

Figure 1: Dispersion curves of leaky Lamb waves in an epoxy waveguide embedded in aluminium [2].

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Intelligent sensor-technology to detect and quantify dangerous damage over large distances in inaccessible areas by using long range multiparameter ultrasound-computed tomography (INTACT)

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Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) plays a crucial role in ensuring the integrity and safety of industrial structures, particularly in the realm of corrosion detection. Guided wave techniques, particularly those excited by Electromagnetic Acoustic Transducers (EMATs), have emerged as promising methods for inspecting large structures such as pipelines, storage tanks, and bridges [1, 2].

The primary objective of the research project INTACT [3] is to develop an effective and reliable method for accurately detecting and characterizing the geometric properties of corrosion defects in metallic pipeline structures. Traditional NDT methods often struggle with inspecting inaccessible or buried pipelines, making early detection of corrosion challenging. Guided wave tomography offers a solution by utilizing guided waves that propagate along the structure, allowing for inspection over large distances and through various materials [4].

The challenges in the INTACT research project include optimizing the arrangement and control of the EMAT sensors as well as data fusion and evaluation in order to achieve maximum sensitivity and resolution in corrosion detection. A well-defined number of different sensor configurations are operated in parallel to capture both transmission and reflection signals from corrosion defects at different angles of incidence relative to the axial direction of the pipe. This approach (signal information at varying angles of incidence) enables the reconstruction of a comprehensive picture of the internal structure and facilitates the precise localization and sizing of corrosion anomalies. Furthermore, the research investigates advanced signal processing techniques to enhance the quality of the acquired data and improve defect characterization. Signal processing algorithms are employed to extract meaningful information from the received signals, such as the amplitude, time-of-flight, and phase, allowing for accurate assessment of corrosion severity and morphology.

This research significantly advances non-destructive testing by enhancing sensor configurations and signal processing algorithms in INTACT. It particularly focuses on guided wave technology for corrosion detection and quantification. Combining guided wave tomography with EMAT sensors offers multiple benefits, including swift scanning inspections without requiring full pipe access. This approach holds promise for assessing corroded pipelines, crucial given aging infrastructure. By tackling key challenges and leveraging sensor tech and signal processing, this research aims to boost reliability, efficiency, and safety while cutting maintenance costs.

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Resonances at free edges for Lamb waves in continuous elasticity or elastic lattice

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In the presence of free edges for elastic waveguides, the behaviour of Lamb waves is particularly interesting where the different modes couple in a non-trivial way. This coupling is at the origin of an edge resonance phenomenon for Lamb waves in two dimensions, at the end of cylinders and around free holes. In this talk we will present this phenomenon as well as his discrete counterpart for the propagation of 2D vibrations in mass-spring lattice waveguides with free edges.

Analysis of guided acoustic waves in periodically structured plates

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Fibre reinforced polymer plates have a wide range of applications, ranging for aerospace to the automotive industry. Due to their complexity, a reliable method for non-destructive testing of these materials has yet to be developed. Woven fibre reinforced polymers in particular have a periodical internal structure, implying that their acoustic behaviour might exhibit properties found in purpose-built phononic crystals. To ascertain if this is the case, simulations as well as experimental studies are conducted. The Floquet-Bloch theory [1, 2] is applied in a simulative investigation using a model of the internal structure of a polymer plate reinforced by plain woven glass fibres. The resulting band structure indicates the existence of features expected of phononic crystals, such as acoustic band gaps and a periodic occurrence of modes in the wavenumber regime, in fibre reinforced polymer plates. The simulation results are corroborated by experimental data acquired using thermoelastically-excited, broadband ultrasonic waves [3]. Experimental results show the existence of several modes that can be attributed to the internal periodic structure of the specimens in different samples, enabling for example, a determination of the size of the effective unit cell of the material. Further research will show if the evaluation of these features can yield further information that can be used for testing purposes, e.g. to evaluate the quality of matrix-to-fibre adhesion.

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Multiplicity of dispersion spectra of anisotropic elastic plates near zero-group-velocity points

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Frequency-wavenumber spectra are of fundamental interest when studying guided waves. In anisotropic media, the power flux of waves may not be aligned with the wave vector [1]. This can lead to the unfolding of one mode into multiple branches in the mentioned spectra [2]. As an example, in Fig. 1 we show the S1/S2b modes (both on the third symmetric modal sheet) of a monocrystalline silicon plate of 525 μm thickness, where a set of intertwining curves are observed in the frequency-wavenumber space. Computations were performed with GEWtool [3]. We show that, independent of the degree of anisotropy, the effect occurs naturally in the vicinity of zero-group-velocity (ZGV) points. The line scan detects waves whose group velocity is aligned with the scan direction, which are the so-called “stationary-phase points” [1]. Multiple curves can be observed when, for any given frequency, multiple wave vectors exhibit the same group-velocity direction, as is visualized in Fig. 1a. Note that the group velocity vectors are always orthogonal to the isofrequency contours.

We generate guided waves with a thermo-elastic laser source and detect them with a laser interferometer on a displacement stage that is sensitive to out-of-plane mechanical displacements. The model is in very good agreement with the experimental spectrum. Moreover, the measurements confirm the extreme power flux skewing induced by the ZGV points, i.e., the angle between the wave vector and the group velocity vector attains values in the range from 0° to 360° . Among other applications, the work opens opportunities for the characterization of complex anisotropic materials.

Figure 1: Different representations of the S1/S2b modes observed with a point-source and a line-scan along \mathbf{e}_X , which is 22.5° out of the [110] crystal axis. **(a)** Iso-frequency contours of the dispersion surface oriented such that the observation direction \mathbf{e}_X is horizontal. The stationary phase points marked therein in dark (light) green are the waves observable to the right (left) of the source. **(b)** Stationary phase points as frequency $\omega/2\pi$ vs. horizontal wavenumber k_X . **(c)** Measured spectral magnitude obtained by scanning across the point source vs. the theoretical stationary phase points from (b).

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Zero-Group-Velocity Lamb modes in a thickness gradient

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Laser ultrasonic techniques are commonly used to generate and detect elastic guided waves, such as Lamb modes, to evaluate the elastic parameters of the probed sample. Among these modes, ZGV Lamb modes combine a zero-group-velocity with a finite wavelength. Therefore, their energy is trapped under the excitation area, enabling local measurements with high sensitivity. Being contactless, laser ultrasonic techniques are powerful tools to observe these ZGV modes, which have been shown to provide precise and local evaluation of the thickness and Poisson's ratio [1–3]. To map the thickness, the plate is usually scanned with the pump and the probe laser beams at the same point. This requires the surface to have high reflectivity and to be perpendicular to the probe at each position. This presentation will explore the possibility of fixing the probe beam while scanning only the excitation beam.

Measurements have been carried out on millimeter-thick Duralumin plates containing thickness gradients. The elastic waves are generated by a pulsed laser ($\lambda=1064$ nm, with 10 ns and a few mJ pulses) and are detected by an interferometric probe ($\lambda=532$ nm). Thickness scans are performed for reference measurement by shifting the sample with co-focused beams. Then, the probe is kept fixed while the source is scanned. The results are compared with a theoretical model [4]. We demonstrate that, under conditions that will be discussed, the thickness profile can be reconstructed from the frequency-dependent amplitude of a ZGV mode even with a fixed probe.

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Experimental challenges of guided wave tomography based on full waveform inversion for a pipe bend

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Pipe bends are considered critical areas prone to wall thinning due to sudden changes in fluid flow direction and velocity. Conventional monitoring techniques for these bends typically depend on localized ultrasonic thickness measurements. While effective, these methods can be time-consuming compared to the use of permanently installed transducers, as utilized in Guided Wave Tomography (GWT). However, the successful implementation of GWT primarily requires (a) an accurate acoustic forward model and (b) calibration of the observed data. Two-dimensional models for guided wave propagation have been proposed, but experimental uncertainties remain a topic of research. In this work, the challenges of experimental uncertainties for the successful implementation of GWT based on full waveform inversion (FWI) for a pipe bend are highlighted, with a focus on the performance of the transducers. A robust methodology is proposed to reduce the experimental uncertainties arising from the transducers, and the observed data is rescaled by considering the phase and amplitude distribution. An experimental evaluation was conducted to reconstruct a defect artificially created on a pipe bend with a diameter (d) of 220 mm and a bend radius of $1.5d$, and a defect with a diameter of 100 mm and a depth of 47%. Reducing experimental uncertainties provides a more accurate representation of the defect and avoids becoming trapped in a local minimum, thereby improving the reliability and effectiveness of FWI.

Non-contact inspection of composites and metallic parts using Lamb waves with a MEMS-sensor array

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Both metal- and fiber-composites in safety critical applications require dedicated non-destructive inspection. Currently, these inspections are performed by transmitting high-frequency ultrasound waves through a panel using water coupling with a squirter probe or via immersion. This approach has several limitations, including the need for water coupling and relatively slow inspection speeds.

An alternative dry, non-contact approach has been developed using low-cost MEMS-sensor technology. The inspection method employs low-frequency Lamb waves to fill a metal or composite panel completely with ultrasound. A fraction of the wave energy radiates into the surrounding air, where it is detected by a MEMS-sensor array at a large stand-off (≈ 100 mm). Simultaneously, integrated laser scanners measure the geometric shape of the part under inspection. This shape is essential for back-propagating the measured wavefield to the surface of the part, effectively simulating measurements taken directly at the surface. Through wavenumber-based processing, the backpropagated wavefield is transformed into a thickness map (see Figure 1). This transformation relies on the dispersion relation of the material, allowing for accurate thickness measurement.

Figure 1: Data of a GLARE2 panel with varying thickness and defects. On the left a time slice of the backpropagated wavefield. On the right the corresponding thickness map, indicating the presence of four different thickness layers and multiple defects of three different sizes. The thickness map provides insight into the structural integrity and defect characterization of the panel.

The current arrays contain 128 MEMS microphones with a pitch of 3 mm, capable of detecting ultrasound up to 250 kHz. These arrays can be mounted on a robotic arm or a multiaxial scanner. Given the array dimensions and translation velocity of the scanning system, potentially inspection speeds of $1 \text{ m}^2/\text{min}$ can be achieved. The method can be used to detect various types of defects, including disbonds, inclusions, delamination, cracks, weld quality, porosity and impact damage. It requires only one-sided access to the part. The methodology will be demonstrated for quality assurance on various metal- and fiber-composite panels, including those equipped with stringers.

Transformer-based Signal Processing

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Methods from the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for processing sensor data are already being used successfully in industrial environments, for example in process monitoring or predictive maintenance. These AI technologies have proven to be innovative tools, especially when analysing complex and multivariate data, and their importance has increased significantly in recent years [1, 2]. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are particularly suitable for processing complex data or directly analysing raw data such as images, time series and sensor signals without the need for manual feature extraction. An advanced approach to processing sequential data utilizes the Transformer architecture, which is based on techniques such as positional encoding and self-attention mechanisms [3]. These mechanisms allow Transformers to overcome the limitations of traditional models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). The architecture enables parallel processing of sequential input data and the recognition of temporal and spatial dependencies within the data. Originally developed for Natural Language Processing (NLP), Transformer models have significantly outperformed RNNs in terms of prediction quality and performance in recent years. Pre-trained Language Models such as BERT or GPT are now considered the new standard in NLP [4, 5]. The application of this architecture is increasingly extending to other fields such as image and sensor data processing, which is currently the subject of intensive research [6, 7].

This study investigated the suitability of the Transformer architecture for processing sensor data, focusing on the analysis of one-dimensional sensor data such as ultrasound or SAW signals. A central challenge is that Transformers are usually most effective when extensive training datasets are available. This represents a significant limitation in areas with restricted data quantities. To overcome this issue, the technique of generative pre-training was employed. In the first step, the raw sensor data are masked and reconstructed to create an abstract and contextualized representation of the input data in the Transformer. Subsequently, the generatively pre-trained model can be fine-tuned with labeled data for specific downstream tasks. Using the example of absolute runtime determination of ultrasound signals, it was demonstrated that generative pre-training can significantly enhance the performance of Transformers. In particular, the reliability of these models greatly exceeded that of untrained models. Additionally, the need for training data was significantly reduced.

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Local resonances and transverse-group-velocity waves in a silicon plate

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Zero-group-velocity (ZGV) modes are local resonances of infinite plates. In anisotropic media they exist only along a finite set of directions [1]. Waves in the vicinity of ZGV points exhibit large skew angles, i.e., the power flux is not collinear to the wave vector. Extreme cases are transverse-group-velocity (TGV) waves, whose power flux is orthogonal to the wave vector [1]. In Fig. 1 (top), we show a laser-ultrasonic measurement of TGV waves obtained on a monocrystalline silicon wafer of cubic anisotropy. Due to the power flux of TGV waves, time acts as a filter in the wavenumber domain. After some time, only eight wave vectors remain close to the source: the ZGV resonances located on the $\langle 100 \rangle$ axes (ZGV1) and the $\langle 110 \rangle$ axes (ZGV2) of the crystal. This intuitively explains the complex resonance pattern that emerges naturally on the surface of the wafer after an impulsive point source excitation. The two ZGV resonance patterns obtained by temporal Fourier transform of the experimentally acquired field are depicted in Fig. 1 (bottom). They form checkerboard patterns, in contrast to the concentric nodal lines seen in isotropic plates. The experimental results are in great agreement with computational predictions with GEWtool [2].

Figure 1: **(top)** Two transverse-group-velocity (TGV) waves radiated by a line source. **(bottom)** Wave field of the ZGV1 and the ZGV2 resonances.

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